

Article

Teacher Education Students' Practices Affecting Their Performance at Public Higher Education Institutions

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Abstract: This study investigates the practices and attitudes of students towards factors affecting their academic performance, encompassing diligence, motivation, pursuit of development, learning habits, and the utilization of out-of-school time. Data collected from a sample predominantly comprising second and fourth-year students reveals a proactive approach towards learning, with high engagement levels in practices that support academic success. Weighted means indicate that students generally practice diligence, motivation, and pursuit of development to a significant extent. However, the study identifies variability in learning habits and out-of-school activities, suggesting areas for improvement. ANOVA tests show no significant differences in practices across year levels, indicating a consistent approach towards academic practices among the respondents. The findings highlight the students' commendable engagement with positive academic behaviors while pointing out potential areas for enhancement, particularly in optimizing learning strategies and out-of-school time management, to further improve educational outcomes.

Keywords: Student Practices, diligence, motivation, learning habits, activities

Introduction

Choosing a school or program that corresponds with your interests is essential for selecting your future profession. Lenci & Scott (2022) emphasized that character development and the acquisition of specific skills and knowledge in preparation for the business world is necessary to achieved students' aspiration. In addition, right course selection can help students fit in their interests and learn more about a field they're genuinely interested in studying (Gonsalves et al., 2021). Moreover, Smith et al. (2021) noted that it is extremely important for students to understand their passion and have clarity about the course they are willing to pursue.

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University is the final stop before entering the workforce and there are many factors to consider, but arguably the most essential is whether you feel at home on campus and are satisfied with the courses you select (Bell & Blanchflower, 2020). Family support, academic preparedness, life skills, and the student's ability to make sound decisions are frequently crucial to a student's college success (Mahoney et al., 2021). Often, the first semester is a revealing moment when a student makes independent judgments and discovers the real-world benefits and repercussions (Yeager et al., 2019).

However, according to regardless of the student's level of independence, a successful transition to college frequently begins with solid family support. For some students, financial aid is essential for enrolling in and beginning school (Contreras-Mendez & Cruse, 2021). Students frequently rely on their parents, siblings, and other family members to coach them through the adjustment and listen when times are tough (Michelson et al., 2021). Strong peer networks and social interaction become essential in the school context. Pupils must experience a sense of belonging and be able to rely on their peers to encourage and keep them accountable for their work. In addition, the requirements for outside-of-class work, reading, and studying often increase substantially between high school and college. Without solid academic habits, those who got by or did well in high school with minimum effort can languish (Lakin & Wai, 2020). Effective academic habits include maintaining a schedule, allocating study time, going to bed on time, attending all courses, utilizing academic assistance services, and visiting with instructors as needed. Although you can receive guidance and establish these habits as a new student, forming solid academic habits in high school gives you a strong success tendency (Looi et al., 2023).

Balancing is often the key to the success of college students. It is crucial to strike a balance between the obligations of being an independent adult and the benefits of independence from parents and home rules (Bahr et al., 2020). A college student can prevent stress by managing money and making sensible financial decisions. Life skill areas that contribute to student success include doing laundry, maintaining good cleanliness, exercising and eating healthily, and getting enough sleep. Students who are easily distracted by excessive social opportunities, alcohol, and drugs may have difficulty attending class and performing well academically. The success or failure of a college student is frequently determined by decisions taken before to and at the beginning of college (Alyahyam & Dustegor, 2020). This begins with picking the appropriate institution, program, and courses that excite and drive the student to study. Important at school is choosing to prepare for an exam or complete an assignment over attending the newest party. Selecting the appropriate chances for social engagement and peer interactions can contribute to the development of a support system and academic achievement (Mishra, 2020).

Moreover, according to Ibanez et al. (2020) motivation in education can have a significant effect on student performance and outcomes. Hence, parents and instructors who wish to assist their children in improving their academic performance should be aware of the aspects that influence student motivation. Motivation is the state that may sustain pupils' attention and behavior, as well as supply them with the additional energy required to complete activities. Hence, it can assist sustain activities over time. Motivation can have a number of implications on the behavior, preferences, and outcomes of students in education. For example, motivation can help us direct our attention toward tasks that need to be completed, allow us to complete these tasks in shorter amounts of time as well as maintain attention for longer periods of time, minimize distractions and resist them more effectively, affect the amount of information we retain and store, and influence the perception of how easy or difficult tasks may appear. Motivation primarily motivates us to undertake an action. Without it, the action may be difficult or impossible to complete (Hauser & Schwarz, 2020).

In addition, the development of any nation is hinged on solid educational foundation for its citizenry (Ekpa et al., 2020). This suggests that education is a means of effecting changes in the society in order to build a well-developed country and education enables a child to develop physically, mentally, socially, emotionally and intellectually (Irene et al., 2022). Therefore, it is axiomatic that efforts should be geared towards maintaining high standards in schools. Like in all other facets of national planning and development, education has its own share of poignant challenges. Academic problems, and less motivation, less family and peer support are frequent reason why students do not continue in college. Problems of non-achievers are numerous but the truth is that they lack the knowledge of their abilities and strengths, moreover, they have not developed the necessary study skills and techniques and they also lack the interest and motivation that are requisite for achievement. Given the importance of literature above, however in the context of BECED students the issues regarding the factors that affect the continuance of their study is scarce. Thus, this study will be conducted

Methodology

In this study, the descriptive research method was employed to meticulously capture and analyze the characteristics and current conditions of the study's population, focusing on students at Cordova Public College during the academic year 2022-2023. This approach was aimed at answering fundamental questions about who the subjects are, what their conditions entail, where they are located, when the study occurs, and how their needs and aptitudes interact. The research hinged on an Input-Process-Output model, ensuring a structured examination of the collected data. To achieve its objectives, the study utilized two

primary research instruments. The first, a Student Demographic Profile Sheet, was a survey designed to collect comprehensive demographic information on the students, including age, gender, year level, parental education and occupation, family income, and permanent address. The second instrument, a Faculty Demographic Profile Sheet, gathered similar data from the college's faculty, focusing on age, gender, educational background, and years of service. Additionally, to assess student aptitude, a methodology adopted from Avilado et al. (2018) was applied, using a 5-point Likert scale ranging from strongly agree to strongly disagree.

Results and Discussion

Table 1. Year Level of the Student Respondents

Year Level	f	%
Fourth Year	16	39.02
Third Year	6	14.63
Second Year	19	46.34
Total	41	100.00

Table 1 provides an overview of the year levels of the respondents in the study, with counts and percentages for each year level. In the "Fourth Year" category, 16 respondents (39.02% of the total respondents) were included, indicating that a significant portion of the sample is in their fourth year of academic study. The "Third Year" category consisted of 6 respondents (14.63% of the total respondents), suggesting a smaller representation of students in their third year. The largest group of respondents was in the "Second Year" category, with 19 individuals (46.34% of the total respondents) belonging to this year level. Overall, the data on year levels of the respondents shows that the sample is predominantly composed of students in their second and fourth years of academic study. This distribution can be important when analyzing the responses and considering potential differences in experiences, practices, and perspectives among students at different stages of their educational journey. It may also be relevant for identifying specific challenges or opportunities that students in various year levels may encounter in their academic pursuits.

The results presented in Table 2 depict the extent to which respondents practice various factors that impact their academic performance, particularly focusing on the theme of student diligence. Across the board, the indicators suggest a high level of engagement and diligence among the students. The aggregate weighted mean (AWM) of 3.86, categorized under "Practiced," indicates that the majority of the behaviors related to academic diligence are not just sporadically but consistently embraced by the students. Notably, the highest rated practice, with a weighted mean (WM) of 4.22, involves thorough

preparation for exams, which falls under the category of "Highly Practiced."

Table 2. Extent to which the Respondents Practice the Identified Factors Affecting their Performance such as Student's Diligence

S/N	Indicators	WM	Verbal Description
1	I consistently achieve impressive scores on my exams, demonstrating my strong understanding of the material.	3.63	Practiced
2	Active participation in all class discussions is a regular practice for me.	3.78	Practiced
3	I am fully attentive during lectures, actively listening to my professors to grasp the information effectively.	4.02	Practiced
4	I actively engage in various extracurricular activities offered at my school.	3.46	Practiced
5	I have developed a habit of regularly studying the notes provided by my professors.	3.76	Practiced
6	I proactively seek additional learning materials to broaden and deepen my knowledge.	3.95	Practiced
7	I demonstrate punctuality and responsibility by always submitting my projects and assignments on time.	4.10	Practiced
8	I ensure thorough preparation for exams by carefully reading and following instructions to minimize errors.	4.22	Highly Practiced
9	I prioritize reviewing the course materials well in advance of the exam day to be fully prepared.	3.85	Practiced
Aggregate Weighted Mean		3.86	Practiced

This reflects a strategic and conscientious approach towards exam preparation, emphasizing the importance of minimizing errors through careful reading and following instructions. Other practices such as punctuality in submitting assignments, active engagement in learning through attentiveness during lectures, and proactive seeking of additional materials for broader knowledge, all received WMs above 3.9, reinforcing the notion that these students take their academic responsibilities seriously. Lower, yet still significant, WMs were observed for practices like engaging in extracurricular activities and regular study of professors' notes, indicating a well-rounded approach to academic excellence that extends beyond the classroom. Overall, the results underscore a collective prioritization of academic diligence among the respondents, which likely contributes positively to their academic performance.

Table 3 provides insight into the factors that influence respondents' academic performance, focusing on their pursuit of personal and academic development. The aggregate weighted mean (AWM) of 4.17, categorized under "Practiced," suggests a strong engagement in behaviors and attitudes that foster growth and learning. Several

indicators received verbal descriptions of "Highly Practiced," notably the commitment to fulfilling promises to family members, with the

Table 3. Extent to which the Respondents Practice the Identified Factors Affecting their Performance such as Pursuit of Development

S/N	Indicators	WM	Verbal Description
1	The materials I need to learn are efficiently designed to maximize my understanding and progress.	4.00	Practiced
2	The teaching strategies I encounter are effective in facilitating my learning and comprehension.	4.12	Practiced
3	I receive valuable support from my family and friends, which motivates and encourages me to succeed.	4.05	Practiced
4	I engage in innovative learning procedures that enhance my educational experience and foster my motivation.	3.95	Practiced
5	The rewards I receive from my guardians serve as further motivation to excel in my studies.	3.93	Practiced
6	I benefit from collective learning with my classmates, fostering a collaborative and supportive environment.	4.00	Practiced
7	I am motivated by the future job opportunities that await me upon graduation, driving my dedication to my studies.	4.32	Highly Practiced
8	I am committed to fulfilling the promise I made to my family members, such as my father, mother, or sister, to succeed in my education.	4.51	Highly Practiced
9	The current life status I am living inspires me to work hard and make the most of the educational opportunities available to me.	4.46	Highly Practiced
10	I strive to cultivate and develop an independent personality that continues to grow over time.	4.39	Highly Practiced
Aggregate Weighted Mean		4.17	Practiced

highest weighted mean (WM) of 4.51. This indicates an exceptionally strong motivational factor tied to personal commitments and relationships. Similarly, the motivation derived from future job opportunities and the drive to improve one's current life status, with WMs of 4.32 and 4.46 respectively, reflect a forward-looking perspective and a strong sense of purpose among the respondents.

The table also highlights the effectiveness of educational materials and teaching strategies, both receiving WMs above 4.00, showing that the respondents find the learning environment conducive to their development. The support from family and friends, alongside rewards from guardians, is recognized as a significant motivational factor, emphasizing the role of a supportive social network in academic success. Engagement in innovative learning procedures and collective learning with classmates are also highly valued, with WMs close to 4.00, pointing to the importance of dynamic and collaborative learning environments. The pursuit of an independent personality, with a WM of 4.39, suggests a strong inclination towards self-improvement and autonomy. Overall, the results from Table 2 indicate a comprehensive approach to development, where respondents value both external support and internal motivation. This holistic engagement with their

education and personal growth pathways not only highlights their dedication but also suggests a positive outlook towards achieving their academic and career goals.

Table 4. Extent to which the Respondents Practice the Identified Factors Affecting their Performance such as Motivation

S/N	Indicators	WM	Verbal Description
1	I actively work towards maturing and gaining the ability to handle various kinds of situations effectively.	4.27	Highly Practiced
2	I consistently seek to enhance my problem-solving skills, enabling me to tackle challenges more effectively.	4.12	Practiced
3	Drawing from my past experiences, I am able to navigate and respond appropriately when faced with similar situations.	4.15	Practiced
4	I adapt seamlessly to different environments, embracing change and using it as an opportunity for growth.	4.15	Practiced
5	With confidence, I present myself in new environments and among diverse crowds.	4.10	Practiced
6	I firmly stand by the decisions I make, taking ownership and responsibility for their outcomes.	4.12	Practiced
7	I am committed to following through on my commitments and fulfilling my obligations.	4.05	Practiced
8	I possess the humility to admit my mistakes and offer sincere apologies when necessary, recognizing the importance of taking responsibility for my actions.	4.22	Highly Practiced
Aggregate Weighted Mean		4.15	Practiced

Table 4 explores the degree to which respondents are motivated by various factors affecting their performance, with a focus on personal growth and adaptability. The aggregate weighted mean (AWM) of 4.15, falling under the category "Practiced," signifies a strong inclination among the students toward self-improvement and responsibility in their actions and decisions. Notably, two indicators stand out with the designation "Highly Practiced": the active work towards maturing and gaining the ability to handle diverse situations effectively, with a weighted mean (WM) of 4.27, and the possession of humility to admit mistakes and offer apologies, with a WM of 4.22. These points underscore a mature approach to personal development, emphasizing resilience, and accountability. The findings also reflect a solid commitment to enhancing problem-solving skills and drawing on past experiences to navigate similar situations in the future, both key components of effective learning and personal growth. The ability to adapt to different environments and embrace change as a growth opportunity further highlights the respondents' resilience and open-mindedness. Presenting oneself confidently in new environments and among diverse groups, along with standing firm by their decisions, are practices that indicate a strong sense of self-assurance and responsibility among the respondents. Moreover, the commitment to fulfilling obligations showcases a reliable and dedicated character.

Table 5. Extent to which the Respondents Practice the Identified Factors Affecting their Performance such as Learning Habits

S/N	Indicators	WM	Verbal Description
1	I utilize online videos as a resource to deepen my understanding of subjects.	3.95	Practiced
2	During my free time, I dedicate myself to reading books and reviewing my notes.	3.49	Practiced
3	Whenever possible, I engage in regular steno-typing practice to improve my skills.	3.22	Moderately Practiced
4	I actively practice typing on keyboards or typewriters to enhance my typing abilities.	3.68	Practiced
5	To ensure thorough preparation, I allocate more time for reviewing in the days leading up to my exams.	3.80	Practiced
6	I find value in group studies, as they make the learning process more enjoyable and collaborative.	3.63	Practiced
7	Proactively, I complete and prepare all my projects and assignments well in advance of their submission dates.	3.90	Practiced
8	Recognizing the importance of rest and rejuvenation, I prioritize getting enough sleep to support my body and brain.	3.80	Practiced
Aggregate Weighted Mean		3.69	Practiced

Table 5 sheds light on the extent to which respondents engage in specific learning habits that affect their performance, reflecting a blend of modern and traditional methods geared towards enhancing their educational experience. The aggregate weighted mean (AWM) of 3.69, categorized under "Practiced," indicates a consistent engagement with various learning strategies, though with varying degrees of adoption. Utilizing online videos as a supplementary resource for deepening subject matter understanding is a popular method among the respondents, with a weighted mean (WM) of 3.95, showcasing a significant inclination towards digital learning tools. This is complemented by more traditional habits like reading books and reviewing notes during free time, albeit with a slightly lower engagement level indicated by a WM of 3.49.

The practice of steno-typing, while still beneficial, is less frequently embraced, with a WM of 3.22, falling under "Moderately Practiced." This suggests a more niche area of skill development among the respondents. Conversely, the broader skill of typing on keyboards or typewriters to enhance typing abilities receives more attention, with a WM of 3.68, highlighting the recognition of typing skills as essential in a digital age. Pre-exam preparations and the strategy of allocating more time for review in the days leading up to exams are well-practiced, with a WM of 3.80, reflecting a conscientious approach to academic success. Group studies also play a significant role in the respondents' learning habits, offering both a collaborative and enjoyable learning process, indicated by a WM of 3.63. Proactivity in completing and preparing projects and assignments well in advance is another highlighted habit, with a WM of 3.90, suggesting a disciplined approach to academic

responsibilities. Additionally, the prioritization of sufficient sleep to support bodily and brain function, with a WM of 3.80, underscores a holistic approach to learning that recognizes the importance of rest and rejuvenation.

Table 6. Extent to which the Respondents Practice the Identified Factors Affecting their Performance such as Out of School Time

S/N	Indicators	WM	Verbal Description
1	I used my time to engaged out of school activities that influence me to study	3.51	Practiced
2	After class my friends and I, reviews the topic that has been discussed	3.20	Moderately Practiced
3	My friends and I, always do a group study	3.12	Moderately Practiced
4	I have my own tutor. He/ She will review my topics	1.71	Not Practiced
5	I am using my vacant time as an opportunity to read my notes	3.39	Moderately Practiced
6	I am using the net to learn new things that may lessen the burden of doing something like life hacks	4.07	Practiced
7	I usually study musical instruments	2.41	Less Practiced
8	I am engaged with sport activities	2.73	Moderately Practiced
9	I am playing video games and any other type of modern computer games that enhances my cognitive aspects.	3.07	Moderately Practiced
Aggregate Weighted Mean		3.02	Moderately Practiced

Table 6 examines how respondents utilize their out-of-school time and the impact of these activities on their academic performance, revealing a diverse range of engagements. The aggregate weighted mean (AWM) of 3.02, categorized under "Moderately Practiced," indicates a varied degree of involvement in activities that could potentially complement their studies. Engaging in out-of-school activities that motivate study habits received a weighted mean (WM) of 3.51, suggesting that students actively seek experiences outside the academic setting that can positively influence their learning mindset. This is closely followed by the use of the internet to learn new things, including life hacks, with a WM of 4.07, highlighting a strong inclination towards leveraging online resources to facilitate easier and more efficient approaches to daily challenges, which could indirectly benefit their academic endeavors. However, certain traditional methods of enhancing academic performance through extracurricular activities are less emphasized. For instance, having a personal tutor to review topics is notably less common, with a WM of 1.71, indicating that this method is not widely practiced among the respondents. Similarly, studying musical instruments and engaging in sports activities are less frequently practiced, with WMs of 2.41 and 2.73 respectively, suggesting that these activities are not as integral to the students' routines in terms of impacting their academic performance. Group studies with friends and reviewing topics discussed in class are seen as moderately practiced, with WMs of 3.12 and 3.20, reflecting a balanced but not predominant preference for collaborative learning outside school hours. The

moderately practiced use of vacant time for reading notes, with a WM of 3.39, further indicates a disciplined yet varied approach to self-directed learning.

Playing video games and engaging in modern computer games, with a WM of 3.07, is recognized to some extent for its potential to enhance cognitive aspects, suggesting an awareness of the benefits these activities can offer in moderation.

Table 7. Test of Difference on the Respondents Practices of the Identified Factors Affecting their Performance such as Student's Diligence when grouped by Year Level

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F-value	P-value	Remarks
Between Groups	87.665	2	43.832	1.138	.331	
Within Groups	1463.360	38	38.509			Not Significant
Total	1551.024	40				

Table 7 presents the statistical analysis for testing differences in the practices of identified factors affecting performance, such as student diligence, when grouped by year level. The "Between Groups" sum of squares, which measures the variance among the different year levels, is 87.665, with a mean square (which is the variance estimate) of 43.832. The "Within Groups" sum of squares, representing the variance within each year level, is substantially higher at 1463.360, with a mean square of 38.509. This indicates that the majority of variance in student diligence practices occurs within individual year levels rather than between them. The F-value, which is used to determine if the variances between groups are significantly different, is 1.138. This is compared against a critical value from an F-distribution based on the degrees of freedom (df) associated with the effect (df between groups = 2) and the error (df within groups = 38). The p-value, which results from comparing the F-value to the distribution, is .331. In the context of ANOVA, a p-value greater than the typical alpha level of 0.05 suggests that there is not enough evidence to conclude that a significant difference exists among the groups. This suggests that factors such as the year of study do not significantly alter how students engage in behaviors associated with diligence, such as attentiveness in class, punctuality in assignments, and preparation for exams.

Table 8. Test of Difference on the Respondents Practices of the Identified Factors Affecting their Performance such as Pursuit of Development when grouped by Year Level

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F-value	P-value	Remarks
Between Groups	18.860	2	9.430	.193	.825	Not Significant
Within Groups	1859.189	38	48.926			
Total	1878.049	40				

Table 8 presents the results of the test of difference on the respondents' practices related to Pursuit of Development when grouped by their respective Year Levels. The objective is to determine whether there are significant differences in the extent to which students pursue personal and academic development based on their Year Level. The table indicates that there is no statistically significant difference in the practices related to Pursuit of Development among the various Year Levels. The F-value of 0.193 is quite low, and the associated p-value of 0.825 is much higher than the typical significance level of 0.05. Consequently, we do not have enough evidence to reject the null hypothesis, suggesting that Year Level does not have a significant impact on how students pursue personal and academic development. This result implies that regardless of their Year Level, students exhibit similar levels of commitment to their personal and academic growth. While the study did not identify significant variations, it highlights the consistency of students' dedication to their development throughout their academic journey.

Table 9. Test of Difference on the Respondents Practices of the Identified Factors Affecting their Performance such as Motivation when grouped by Year Level

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F-value	P-value	Remarks
Between Groups	4.064	2	2.032	.062	.940	
Within Groups	1241.741	38	32.677			Not Significant
Total	1245.805	40				

Table 9 presents the results of the test of difference on the respondents' practices related to Motivation when grouped by their respective Year Levels. The objective is to determine whether there are significant differences in the extent to which students are motivated based on their Year Level. The table shows that there is no statistically significant difference in the practices related to Motivation among the various Year Levels. The F-value of 0.062 is very low, and the associated p-value of 0.940 is much higher than the typical significance level of 0.05. Consequently, we do not have enough evidence to reject the null hypothesis, suggesting that Year Level does not have a significant impact on how students are motivated. This result implies that regardless of their Year Level, students exhibit similar levels of motivation in their academic pursuits. While the study did not identify significant variations, it underscores the consistency of students' motivation throughout their academic journey, highlighting the importance of self-motivation in achieving academic success. Moreover, the consistency of motivation across Year Levels underscores the importance of fostering and maintaining self-motivation as a key driver of academic success. Educators and

institutions can leverage this intrinsic motivation to create an environment that inspires and empowers students throughout their educational journey.

Table 10. Test of Difference on the Respondents Practices of the Identified Factors Affecting their Performance such as Learning Habits when grouped by Year Level

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F-value	P-value	Remarks
Between Groups	103.447	2	51.723	1.786	.181	
Within Groups	1100.797	38	28.968			Not Significant
Total	1204.244	40				

Table 10 presents the results of the test of difference on the respondents' practices related to Learning Habits when grouped by their respective Year Levels. The aim is to determine whether there are significant differences in the extent to which students practice effective learning habits based on their Year Level. The table indicates that there is no statistically significant difference in the practices related to Learning Habits among the various Year Levels. The F-value of 1.786 is relatively low, and the associated p-value of 0.181 is greater than the conventional significance level of 0.05. Consequently, there is insufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis, suggesting that Year Level does not have a significant impact on how students practice learning habits. This finding implies that students across different academic levels tend to exhibit similar learning habits. While this study did not identify substantial variations, it underscores the importance of promoting effective learning habits throughout a student's academic journey. However, it is essential to recognize that other unexplored factors may influence learning habits, warranting further investigation to provide a more comprehensive understanding of this aspect of student performance.

Table 11. Test of Difference on the Respondents Practices of the Identified Factors Affecting their Performance such as Out of School Time when grouped by Year Level

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F-value	P-value	Remarks
Between Groups	217.122	2	108.561	2.614	.086	Not Significant
Within Groups	1577.902	38	41.524			
Total	1795.024	40				

Table 11 presents the results of the test of difference on the respondents' practices related to Out of School Time when grouped by their respective Year Levels. The objective is to determine whether there are significant differences in the extent to which students utilize their out-of-school time for various activities based on their Year Level. The table indicates that there is no statistically significant difference in the practices related to Out of School Time among the different Year Levels.

The F-value of 2.614 is relatively low, and the associated p-value of 0.086 is greater than the typical significance level of 0.05. As a result, there is insufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis, suggesting that Year Level does not have a significant impact on how students utilize their out-of-school time. This finding implies that students across various academic levels tend to allocate their out-of-school time similarly for different activities. However, it is important to note that while this study did not uncover significant differences, individual preferences and external factors may influence how students utilize their free time, making it an area for further investigation and consideration when designing educational support programs.

Conclusion

The analysis of student responses regarding factors affecting their academic performance reveals a proactive and engaged attitude towards learning and personal development. Most respondents, primarily in their second and fourth years, consistently engage in practices that support diligence, motivation, and the pursuit of development, with average ratings suggesting these habits are well-incorporated into their routines. Despite high levels of practice in these areas, the study highlights variability in learning habits and the use of out-of-school time, pointing towards opportunities for further improvement. The absence of significant differences in practices across year levels underscores a uniformity in student culture regarding academic practices. This suggests that while students exhibit commendable dedication to enhancing their academic performance, there remains room for growth in optimizing out-of-school activities and refining specific learning strategies to elevate their educational outcomes further.

References

Alyahyan, E., & Düşteğör, D. (2020). Predicting academic success in higher education: literature review and best practices. *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*, 17, 1-21.

Allal-Chérif, O., Aránega, A. Y., & Sánchez, R. C. (2021). Intelligent recruitment: How to identify, select, and retain talents from around the world using artificial intelligence. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 169, 120822.

Bailey, T. R., & Belfield, C. R. (2019). The false dichotomy between academic learning & occupational skills. *Daedalus*, 148(4), 164-178.

Bahr, P. R., Boeck, C. A., & Cummins, P. A. (2020). Strengthening outcomes of adult students in community colleges. *Higher Education: Handbook of Theory and Research: Volume 36*, 1-57.

Bell, D. N., & Blanchflower, D. G. (2020). US and UK labour markets before and during the Covid-19 crash. *National Institute Economic Review*, 252, R52-R69.

Contreras-Mendez, S., & Cruse, L. R. (2021). *Busy with Purpose: Lessons for Education and Policy Leaders from Returning Student Parents*. Institute for Women's Policy Research.

Ekpa, E., Bature¹, S. A., Kemi, O. E., & Comfort, O. (2022). SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY EDUCATION: CATALYST FOR NIGERIA'S DEVELOPMENT. *Environment*, 7(1), 01-08.

Lenci, S., & Scott, S. (2022). Implementation of Professional Skills into Technical Education Programs. *International Journal for Leadership in Learning*, 22(2), 140-180.

Lakin, J. M., & Wai, J. (2020). Spatially gifted, academically inconvenienced: Spatially talented students experience less academic engagement and more behavioural issues than other talented students. *British Journal of Educational Psychology*, 90(4), 1015-1038.

Looi, C. K., Wong, S. L., Kong, S. C., Chan, T. W., Shih, J. L., Chang, B., ... & Liao, C. C. (2023). Interest-Driven Creator Theory: case study of embodiment in an experimental school in Taiwan. *Research and Practice in Technology Enhanced Learning*, 18

Gonsalves, A. J., Cavalcante, A. S., Sprowls, E. D., & Iacono, H. (2021). "Anybody can do science if they're brave enough": Understanding the role of science capital in science majors' identity trajectories into and through postsecondary science. *Journal of Research in Science Teaching*, 58(8), 1117-1151.

Hauser, D. J., & Schwarz, N. (2020). The war on prevention II: Battle metaphors undermine cancer treatment and prevention and do not increase vigilance. *Health communication*, 35(13), 1698-1704.

Irene, M. T., Simeon, M., Ernest, M., & Margaret, N. (2022). Play-Based Learning as a Strategy to Prepare Grade R Learners for Formal Education in Waterberg District of Limpopo, South Africa. *Creative Education*, 13(10), 3225-3237.

Ibáñez, M. B., Portillo, A. U., Cabada, R. Z., & Barrón, M. L. (2020). Impact of augmented reality technology on academic achievement and motivation of students from public and private Mexican schools. A case study in a middle-school geometry course. *Computers & Education*, 145, 103734.

Law, K. M., & Breznik, K. (2017). Impacts of innovativeness and attitude on entrepreneurial intention: Among engineering and non-engineering students. *International Journal of Technology and Design Education*, 27, 683-700.

Law, K. M., Geng, S., & Li, T. (2019). Student enrollment, motivation and learning performance in a blended learning environment: The mediating effects of social, teaching, and cognitive presence. *Computers & Education*, 136, 1-12.

Mahoney, J. L., Weissberg, R. P., Greenberg, M. T., Dusenbury, L., Jagers, R. J., Niemi, K., ... & Yoder, N. (2021). Systemic social and emotional learning: Promoting educational success for all preschool to high school students. *American Psychologist*, 76(7), 1128.

Mishra, S. (2020). Social networks, social capital, social support and academic success in higher education: A systematic review with a special focus on 'underrepresented' students. *Educational Research Review*, 29, 100307.

Michelson, R., DeWitt, A., Nagar, R., Hiniker, A., Yip, J., Munson, S. A., & Kientz, J. A. (2021). Parenting in a pandemic: juggling multiple roles and managing technology use in family life during COVID-19 in the United States. *Proceedings of the ACM on Human-Computer Interaction*, 5(CSCW2), 1-39.

Smith, Y., Chen, Y. J., & Warner-Stidham, A. (2021). Understanding online teaching effectiveness: Nursing student and faculty perspectives. *Journal of Professional Nursing*, 37(5), 785-794.

Yeager, D. S., Hanselman, P., Walton, G. M., Murray, J. S., Crosnoe, R., Muller, C., ... & Dweck, C. S. (2019). A national experiment reveals where a growth mindset improves achievement. *Nature*, 573(7774), 364-369.